

Sizing Solutions for Upgrading of Carbon Fibres with Nanomaterials Synthesised from Solvolysis Wastes

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Presentation Outline

- **Motivation**
- **Development of formulations**
- **From Lab to Pilot scale**
- **Conclusions**

Motivation

Develop water based nano enhanced sizing solutions to improve compatibility of carbon fibres with resins and improve performance after recycling

Challenges:

Agglomeration of nanomaterials

Stable solutions

Uniform coatings

Upscaling

Circularity: From CFRPs to Nano-Enhanced CFRPs

Advantages:

- **Exploitation of solvolysis wastes** (major issue of the recycling process)
- Synthesis of **high-added value nanomaterials** (e.g. CNTs) from waste streams
- **Enhancement** of reclaimed Carbon Fibres and properties **improvement**
- New **nano-enhanced CFRPs** produced from recycled materials
- **Circularity** in the composites value chain

* CFRP waste: EoL part from B&T made by filament winding
 ** Solvolysis Wastes: By-product of Solvolysis process of SUT
 *** Reclaimed CFs: Achievement of UPATRAS through plasma enhanced solvolysis

Development of formulations

Various organic precursors (hydrocarbons) in liquid form have been used to synthesize CNTs:

Chemical Vapour Deposition Set-Up

a CVD reactor schematic

b Base CNT growth

c Tip CNT growth

Zaytseva & Neumann, Carbon NMs: production, impact on plant development, agricultural and environmental applications. Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric. 3, 17 (2016).

MWCNTs in entangled or aligned form

Y. Xu, et al. Evolution of Nanoparticles in the Gas Phase during the Floating CVD Synthesis of Carbon Nanotubes. J. Phys. Chem. C, 2018, 122 (11), 6437-46.

Different inlet alternatives to introduce the Solvolysis Liquid Waste in the CVD Reactor in R-NanoLab

Introduction through separation funnel

Boiling in conical flask

Boiling in spherical flask

Boiling in two-necked spherical flask

Development of formulations

Michelman HP2-06 as commercial water base sizing (1-2.5-5%) + water dispersed nanomaterials (0.05-0.1-0.25%)

Hielschler Sonication Probe 45m + Triton X

FLG dispersions

- ❖ 2 %wt FLG-O₂ water dispersion
- ❖ 2 %wt FLG-N₂ water dispersion
- ❖ 2 %wt FLG-NH₃ water dispersion

CNT dispersions

- ❖ 2 %wt CNT-O₂ water dispersion
- ❖ 2 %wt CNT-N₂ water dispersion
- ❖ 2 %wt CNT-NH₃ water dispersion

Use of surfactant for CNT dispersions

- Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS)
- Cetrimonium bromide (CTAB)
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- TRITON X 100

- Solid Content Concentration investigation:

5% solids

2.5% solids

1% solids

From lab to pilot scale

From Lab to Pilot scale

100ml of the 18 sizing formulations have been prepared and each one has been used to coat 10 CF bundles of 30cm length at the lab scale apparatus.

Subsequently the fibres have been assessed for their morphological characterization (SEM), affinity with resin (CAG) and mechanical properties (Tensile - 3 p. bend).

For the Mechanical tests the fibres have been impregnated in epoxy resin and left to cure in a 3D printed tool under tension.

More than 200 samples in total were tested under tensile loading and 3 point.

From Lab to Pilot scale

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	7 000 x	10.6 mm	38.6 μm	-0 °	SE

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	7 000 x	10.3 mm	38.6 μm	-0 °	SE

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	7 000 x	9.5 mm	38.6 μm	-0 °	SE

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	20 000 x	10.8 mm	13.5 μm	-0 °	SE

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	20 000 x	10.8 mm	13.5 μm	-0 °	SE

HV	mag	WD	HFW	tilt	mode
20.00 kV	15 000 x	10.3 mm	18.0 μm	-0 °	SE

From Lab to Pilot scale

	Desized	Michelman	CNTs									FLG								
			O2			N2			NH3			O2			N2			NH3		
			0.05	0.1	0.25	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.05	0.1	0.25
3 point	31.3 ± 3	37.1 ± 4.3	35.6 ± 4.5	36.1 ± 5	37.9 ± 3.8	41.8 ± 3.7	44.5 ± 3	34.2 ± 3.5	36.6 ± 2.4	39.1 ± 3.3	37.9 ± 2	41.3 ± 2.7	43.1 ± 6.6	41.9 ± 3.6	43 ± 4.1	45.1 ± 2.8	41.3 ± 3.1	33.6 ± 3	42.2 ± 3.9	34.2 ± 2.6
Tensile	262 ± 31	391 ± 49	317 ± 34	271 ± 24	334 ± 33	430 ± 27	434 ± 12	376 ± 44	333 ± 27	380 ± 32	388 ± 47	343 ± 27	391 ± 49	421 ± 61	391 ± 34	444 ± 39	354 ± 40	441 ± 156	336 ± 41	351 ± 15

From Lab to Pilot scale

1% solids

2.5% solids

5% solids

Conclusions

Challenges:

- Agglomeration of nanomaterials
- Stable solutions
- Effective desizing
- Uniform coatings
- Upscaling

Solutions:

- Hielschler Sonication Probe
- Triton X surfactant
- Few seconds at 600°C
- Control of Solid Content in the sizing formulation
- Addition of nanomaterial can improve mechanical properties

Further Investigation:

- Uniform distribution of nanomaterials onto the CF surface during sizing process

Acknowledgments

**Thank you for
your attention**

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